

Research

Comparative and Synergistic Anti-Oxidative Studies of the Extracts from *Ocimum Sanctum* and *Mentha Piperita*

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Abstract: Tulsi is known as holy basil. Tulsi is used as an anti-oxidant, anti-inflammation, anti-ulcer and anti-septic properties. Tulsi has very important medicinal value. It has great agriculture importance all over the world. Mint is used worldwide in medicine, cookery and for household. Mint used in the treatment of gastro enteric diseases. Antioxidant are a group of substances which, when presented low concentration, in relation to oxidisable substances, significantly inhibit or delay oxidative process, while often being oxidized themselves. Anti-oxidants can scavenge the active form of oxygen involved in the initial step of the oxidation. Their importance in the safe guarding of the health, and the protection from coronary heart disease and cancer. All plants were extracted with the conventional method, reflux with methanol. Tulsi and Mint plant were collected from local home garden. About 11gram of Tulsi and 5.5 gram of mint extract powder was soaked in 70% of methanol by continues shaking. Extract was filter with the help of filter paper and to check high percentage antioxidant activity kept for 7 days. H₂O₂ and Ascorbic acid were used as reference and control. After adding these sample were pass through 400 nm wave length and obtained result. As we know greater absorbance, low will be the antioxidant activity. Mint has greater antioxidant activity than Tulsi. Result showed that absorbance of mint is higher than the absorbance of Tulsi.

Keywords: Antioxidants, *Ocimum*, *Mentha*, Free radicals

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Introduction

Holy basil (*Ocimum sanctum*) is included in the family Lamiaceae, along with several other medicinal herbs such as salvia and mint and over 65 species of basil that are used in the food, pharmacology and perfume industry. The species is closely related to sweet basil (*Ocimum basilicum*), a commonly used herb in Europe and North America. Holy basil has also been described as *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (basil with small flowers) or *Ocimum gratissimum* (very grateful basil). Of these, the species name *O. sanctum* is favored due to the wide range of its uses in religious and cultural traditions (Brinckmann et al., 2013).

Holy Basil: The Elixir of Life

Traditional uses of holy basil as medicine usually include, but are not limited to the treatment of: abdominal issues, oral infections, cough, colds, tumours and cancer, digestive tract problems, respiratory inflammation, arthritis, asthma, ulcers, wounds, hypoglycaemia, bronchitis, urinary issues, cardiovascular problems and many others. Although the whole plant is medicinally important, the leaves are generally the most common form of treatment, and are either used raw or steeped in hot water. The medicinal properties of holy basil leaves include: antioxidant, antimicrobial, anticancer, antistress, adaptogenic, stimulant, expectorant, nervine, antipyretic and antiperiodic. These beneficial properties have led to holy basil being named “Queen of Herbs”, “Incomparable One” and “The Mother Medicine of Nature” and one of the most valued medicinal and religious herbs in India. The knowledge of this traditional medicinal herb is expanding to other cultures due to its unique therapeutic properties (Brinckmann et al., 2013).

Production of Holy Basil

Holy basil is an important part of the agricultural system in all over the world and is among one of the 178 highly cultivated plant species and one of only 36 species with stabilised local agricultural systems (Ved and Goraya, 2008). The consumption of holy basil is approximately 3500MT annually, with trade requirements between 2000 – 5000 MT, sourced through traditional cultivation practices (Engels et al., 2013, Nadir et al., 2022).

Basil plants have small seeds that require friable, well tilled soil and which are planted in late spring (April – May). Germination of seeds, planted in rows 10-15cm apart and with plants 2cm apart, occurs after 4 - 14 days. It is common to see variation in the production and appearance of the plants based on the environmental alterations. Using a fertilizer with a 1:1:1 ratio of P, K, N is desirable, and the species is not water tolerant so a consistent, slow application of water is ideal. The plant grows well under long days and high temperatures, preferably in full sun, but can tolerate partial shade (Kew, 2004, Nadir et al., 2022). Removal of the inflorescence enhances vegetative growth and results in a flush of new leaves throughout the growing season. In tropical climate, the first holy basil crop can be harvested in about three months and under optimized growth conditions, as many as three to four harvests are easily possible. The method of harvest affects overall yield of essential oil content as well as individual components of the oil. For example, secondary branches were found to have decreased biomass but increased essential oil content with high levels of eugenol, and low levels of methyl-eugenol – two main chemical components of holy basil. The biomass harvested from above 30cm from ground had decreased essential oil yield (Kothari et al., 2004).

Medicinal Properties of Holy Basil

Medicinal effect on holy basil is believed to be due to the complexity of constituents in the plant, leading to many positive influences in the human body. Innumerable medicinal benefits of holy basil have been recorded in many different regions and local languages around world. Recently, scientific evidence of therapeutic effect of holy basil has started to emerge in mainstream medical journals mostly from studies using *in vitro* bioassays and small clinical trials. A few recent examples of such studies on holy basil include: antimetastatic activity against Lewis Lung carcinoma cells, cardio protective inhibition of lipid peroxidation in rats induced with myocardial infarction, and high cholesterol or high cadmium diets, neuroprotection and normalization of brain function through modulation of neurotransmitters (Ahmad et al., 2012) and prevention of radiation mediated cell death in mice. Other examples of the medicinal properties of holy basil are antimicrobial benefits as a mouth rinse, inhibition of bacterial gonorrhoeal, anthelmintic activity, wound healing

and reduced levels of plasma glucose, triglyceride and cholesterol Holy basil can also reduce diabetic symptoms and blood pressure and stimulate insulin production in the pancreas as well as, subdue skin, breast, and gastric cancer because of the anti-oxidative properties (Baliga et al., 2013).

Although the most widespread use of holy basil remains to be medicinal, recent studies have shown that this plant is effective against a variety of biological pollutants present in water. Holy basil essential oils have antifungal and anti-aflatoxigenic effects which can be used for storage and improvement of shelf life of food products such as 'Tofu'. There is evidence that holy basil extracts can improve the shelf life of bananas and may also be a viable alternative to chemical fungicides for the management of crown rot disease. Strong antimicrobial effects of the essential oil constituents against pathogenic fungi and both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria have also been demonstrated (Sangeetha et al., 2010).

Chemistry:

A wide range of technologies have been used for the quantification of the chemical composition as well as antioxidant potential of holy basil including gas chromatography (GC), high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC), GC-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopic analysis, solid phase microextraction (SPME), flame ionization detection (FID), and olfactic evaluation (Amber et al., 2010). Antioxidant potentials have been measured separately by assays such as DPPH (1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl), and TBARS (thiobarbitonic acid reactive substances) or have been combined with HPLC (high performance liquid chromatography) (Trevisan et al., 2006). Techniques such as x-ray fluorescence analysis and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy coupled with principal component analysis have been used to evaluate the uniformity and identity of herbal plants for quality control purposes (Morabad and Kerur., 2010).

The chemical composition of holy basil analyzed by multiple techniques described above revealed a highly complex mixture of many nutrients, essential oils and other biologically active compounds. The plant contains a diverse range of compounds including alkaloids, carbohydrates, fats, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, proteins, saponins, tannins and terpenes. Generally, the main components of the leaf tissue are eugenol and methyl-eugenol but their levels vary in different plants. These constituents along with the numerous other compounds found in holy basil at lower levels, give rise to the variety in medicinal properties (Trevisan et al., 2006).

Antioxidants in Plants

Antioxidants scavenge free radicals within the body and externally. Free radicals are unstable and react with cell membranes, proteins, DNA and lipids causing structural and functional damage. This is undesirable as it can lead to premature aging of the cells, causing degenerative diseases, cancer and cardiovascular problems and other health issues. Antioxidants provide protection by offering a free proton and are oxidized themselves, thereby stopping the oxidation chain reaction (Halliwell et al., 2009).

Mint:

Mint peppery (*Mentha piperita*) is one of the most widespread types of herbs. It is widely used in medicine, cookery, and household, as well as pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry. Mint is applied as a medication in the form of infusions and teas for treatment of gastroenteric diseases, as demulcent at palpitation, depression and insomnia, in sedatives, as anesthesia at burns and insect stings, as well as analgesic and antistress medicine. Antioxidant properties of mint allow to prevent cataract and other illnesses connected with ageing of an organism. Mint peppery basic component (2–3 %) is menthol defining its taste and anesthetizing properties. Other substances contained are ethers, phellandrene, pinene, jasmole, piperitone, menthofuran, etc. There are also tannic and resinous substances, carotin (0.01 %), ascorbic acid (0.01 %), routines (0.015 %), and other polyphenolic compounds. In the literature there are publications devoted to measurement of the AO quantity and activity in extracts of mint. However, these are basically complex chemical methods, and the results received are poorly comparable among themselves, including the absence of uniform

measuring units while the use of two operative electrochemical methods allows studying the antioxidant activity of mint after extraction (Kosygin et al., 2011).

Free Radicals

The body is under constant attack from oxidative stress. Oxygen in the body splits into single atoms with unpaired electrons. Electrons like to be in pairs, so these atoms, called free radicals, scavenge the body to seek out other electrons so they can become a pair. This causes damage to cells, proteins and DNA. Free radicals are associated with human disease, including cancer, atherosclerosis, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and many others. They also may have a link to aging, which has been defined as a gradual accumulation of free-radical damage, according to Christopher Wanjek, the Bad Medicine columnist for Live Science. Substances that generate free radicals can be found in the food we eat, the medicines we take, the air we breathe and the water we drink, according to the Huntington's Outreach Project for Education at Stanford University. These substances include fried foods, alcohol, tobacco smoke, pesticides and air pollutants.

Free radicals are the natural byproducts of chemical processes, such as metabolism. Dr. Lauri Wright, a registered dietitian and an assistant professor of nutrition at the University of South Florida, said, "Basically, I think of free radicals as waste products from various chemical reactions in the cell that when built up, harm the cells of the body." Yet, free radicals are essential to life, The body's ability to turn air and food into chemical energy depends on a chain reaction of free radicals. Free radicals are also a crucial part of the immune system, floating through the veins and attacking foreign invaders (Wanjek et al., 2006).

The danger of free radicals

According to Rice University, once free radicals are formed, a chain reaction can occur. The first free radical pulls an electron from a molecule, which destabilizes the molecule and turns it into a free radical. That molecule then takes an electron from another molecule, destabilizing it and turning it into a free radical. This domino effect can eventually disrupt and damage the whole cell.

The free radical chain reaction may lead to broken cell membranes, which can alter what enters and exits the cell, according to the Harvard School of Public Health. The chain reaction may change the structure of a lipid, making it more likely to become trapped in an artery. The damaged molecules may mutate and grow tumors or the cascading damage may change DNA code.

Oxidative stress occurs when there are too many free radicals and too much cellular damage. Oxidative stress is associated with damage of proteins, lipids and nucleic acids, according to an article in the Pharmacognosy Review. Several studies throughout the last few decades have suggested that oxidative stress plays a role in the development of many conditions, including macular degeneration, cardiovascular disease, certain cancers, emphysema, alcoholism, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, ulcers and all inflammatory diseases, such as arthritis and lupus. Free radicals are also associated with aging. "The free radical theory of aging states that we age because of free radical damage over time," said Wright. Free radicals can damage DNA's instructional code, causing our new cells to grow incorrectly, leading to aging

(Usha et al., 2010).

Symptoms of oxidative stress

According to a 2010 article in Methods of Molecular Biology, there are no officially recognized symptoms of oxidative stress. According to naturopathic doctor Donielle Wilson's website, however, symptoms include fatigue, headaches, noise sensitivity, memory loss and brain fog, muscle and joint pain, wrinkles and gray hair, vision trouble and decreased immunity

(Usha et al., 2010).

Testing for free radicals

It is not possible to directly measure the amount of free radicals in the body, according to Rice University. According to a 2000 article in the American Journal of Clinical Nutrition, there are indirect methods of measuring oxidative stress, usually involving analysis of the byproducts of lipid peroxidation. The article warns that all methods should "should be used with caution because of the lack of accuracy, validity or both." The more recent article in Methods of Molecular Biology states that kits for testing oxidative stress are increasingly available, though their accuracy and validity are still under scrutiny (Usha et al., 2010).

Antioxidants and free radicals

Antioxidants keep free radicals in check. Antioxidants are molecules in cells that prevent free radicals from taking electrons and causing damage. Antioxidants are able to give an electron to a free radical without becoming destabilized themselves, thus stopping the free radical chain reaction. "Antioxidants are natural substances whose job is to clean up free radicals. Just like fiber cleans up waste products in the intestines, antioxidants clean up the free radical waste in the cells," said Wright. Well-known antioxidants include beta-carotene and other carotenoids, lutein, resveratrol, vitamin C, vitamin E, lycopene and other phytonutrients (Parg et al., 2010).

Our body produces some antioxidants on its own, but an insufficient amount. Oxidative stress occurs when there is an imbalance of free radicals and antioxidants (too many free radicals and too few antioxidants), according to the Pharmacognosy Review. Antioxidants can be acquired through diet (Thomas et al., 2006).

H₂O₂ Free Radical

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is a strong oxidizer. You may know it as a wound disinfectant or as a bleaching agent for hair and teeth but it is also created naturally in our bodies, as part of our cellular oxidation.

H₂O₂ belongs to a group of natural chemicals called reactive oxygen species (ROS) and when the process gets out of hand, too much oxidation can have a damaging effect on cells and their components. Unchecked free radicals, the most well-known ROS, are believed to play a role in carcinogenesis, degenerative diseases, and even aging. To prevent that, our cells also contain antioxidant enzymes known as peroxiredoxins that degrade H₂O₂ molecules. We don't want to have no H₂O₂, despite the chemophobia of environmental and food activists, we want just enough. "Under most conditions, H₂O₂ is not an undesired side product but rather an essential chemical messenger that plays an important role in regulating the way in which body cells respond to signals from outside such as hormones and growth factors," says Dr. Tobias of the German Cancer Research Center. "We know today that the body's own H₂O₂ is vital for signal processing in a healthy organism (Morasuk et al., 2007).

H₂O₂ transmits signals by oxidizing specific proteins at particular sites, thereby alternatively turning them on or off. Team have shown the molecular mechanisms behind this signaling through specific oxidation in human cells, a mechanism that has long been enigmatic for scientists. A signaling molecule needs to act specifically. How can a tiny molecule like H₂O₂, which is hardly any larger than a water molecule (H₂O), specifically oxidize particular proteins while leaving others completely unaffected? And why is it that the relatively small amounts of H₂O₂ that are produced for signaling are not immediately captured by peroxiredoxins before H₂O₂ can even react with target proteins? "Tumor cells produce larger quantities of H₂O₂ and use oxidative signals at higher levels than normal cells in order to drive their own growth," says Mirko Sobotta, first author of the publication. "Now that we have identified the peroxiredoxins as key players in specific oxidation, we can target them in order to interfere with cancer-relevant oxidative signals (Ramesh et al., 2004)

Aim and Objectives

Natural products have been playing a vital role in health care for decades. There are different sources of natural products, plants have been a source of chemical substance. The aim of the research is to compare and correlate the synergistic anti-oxidant activity of Tulsi and Mint.

The objective of the study are;

- Extraction from Tulsi and Mint Plant
- Preparation of the stocks from both extracts individually
- Preparation of the sub stocks from previous stocks
- Making combination stocks and sub stocks.
- Measuring percentage antioxidant values.

Research Methodology

Collection of Plant Material

Collected plant from local home garden at Ghori Town Islamabad in month of July 2018.

Tulsi and Mint plants material was identified.

Preparation of plant extract

About 11 gram of Tulsi and 5.5 gram of Mint plant extract powder was soaked in 300 ml of methanol (70%) by continuous shaking. The extract was then filtered with the help of qualitative filter paper after 168 hours (7 days). When filtration was done then with the help water bath organic solvents was removed. The extract was then placed into water bath to evaporate remaining methanol at 40°C as shown in table no 1. For in-vitro studies, methanolic extract of Tulsi and Mint was kept in the refrigerator at 4°C.

Extracts	Concentration 1	Concentration 2	Concentration 3	Concentration 4
Mint	200	400	600	800
Tulsi	200	400	600	800
Combined	200	400	600	800
Sub Stock	200 CS* + 800ml Mt**	400CS + 600 Mt	600CS + 400 Mt	800CS + 200 Mt

Table 1. Extracts and Concentration of *Ocimum sanctum* and *Mentha piperita*

*CS= Combined Stock

**Mt= Methanol

Antioxidant assays

H₂O₂ was use as free radical and percentage antioxidant activity of Tulsi Leaf Extract (TLE) and Mint Leaf Extract (MLE) was measure by studying the breakdown of H₂O₂.

Procedure

Preparation of stock and sub solution from each extracts of Tulsi and Mint

By mixing 0.006g from each extracts of Tulsi and Mint in 6ml of methanol, stock solution was prepared. Sub solutions were prepared in methanolic tubes as concentration of 200µg/ml, 400µg/ml, 600µg/ml and 800µg/ml from each stock of Mint and Tulsi.

Preparation of combined stock and sub stock concentration

Mixing both the extract of mint and Tulsi in the concentration of 0.003gm making the total concentration of 0.006gm. then different sub stocks were made of different concentration starting from 200µL to 800 µL.

Addition of H₂O₂ stock solution

H₂O₂ was taken and dissolve completely in 100ml methanol. Now from each sub stocks concentration (200µg/ml, 400µg/ml, 600µg/ml and 800µg/ml) of both about 200µL of plan extract was taken and mixed with 800µL of H₂O₂ solution.

Preparation of ascorbic acid

Ascorbic acid was also prepared by the same process which was used as a reference.

The tubes were then kept in dark for incubation at 37°C for 25 minutes.

Preparation of stock and sub solution

Stock solution was prepared by taking 0.006g of extract and dissolved well in 6ml of methanol. Sub solution was prepared in tubes as 100µg/ml, 400µg/ml, 600µg/ml and 800µg/ml. These concentrations (100µg/ml, 400µg/ml 600µg/ml and 800µg/ml) were then sprayed on the Petri plates.

Adding H₂O₂ to standard

With the help of digital balance about 0.006g ascorbic acid was taken and dissolved completely in 1ml of stock solution of Tulsi and mint. H₂O₂ was used as positive control. For negative control only 1ml H₂O₂ media was used.

Procedure

All 16 micro centrifuge tubes kept in refrigerator for further study. Stock include four tube of Tusli, four tube of Mint, four sub stock tubes and four tubes of reference ascorbic acid. After 4 days with the help of Spectrophotometry absorbance were find out.

Measurement of Absorbance:

Initially absorbance value of H₂O₂ was determine by spectrophotometer which was set at 400 nm, the results was 0.16 nm. Then absorbance of Ascorbic acid samples were determine by same process at 400 nm, results comes from 0.13 nm to 0.22 nm. After the Tulsi and Mint sample were determined by same process ate 400 nm.

Percentage antioxidant activity was measured by the formula

$$\text{Scavenging} = \text{Concentration} * \text{Sample absorbance} / \text{Concentration} * 100$$

Results

In this study mint and Tulsi antioxidant activity of both were compared and it was focused to know their synergetic effects. Absorbance value obtained via spectrophotometer. Antioxidant activity is indirectly proportion to absorbance values. Absorbance value increases and Antioxidant value decreases shown in table no 2 and 3.

Sample	Wavelength	Absorbance
Tulsi Sample 1	400	0.13nm
Tulsi Sample 2	400	0.18nm
Tulsi Sample 3	400	0.08nm
Tulsi Sample 4	400	0.19nm

Table 2. The absorbance range of Tulsi on 400 nm wavelength of Spectrophotometer

Sample	Wavelength	Absorbance
Mint (Sample 1)	400	0.16nm
Mint (Sample 2)	400	0.22nm
Mint (Sample 3)	400	0.23nm
Mint (Sample 4)	400	0.26nm

Table no 3. The absorbance range of Tulsi on 400 nm wavelength of Spectrophotometer.

Sample	Wavelength	Absorbance
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Mixed Stock Sample 1	400	0.15nm
Mixed Stock (Sample 2)	400	0.20nm
Mixed Stock (Sample 3)	400	0.13nm
Mixed Stock (Sample 4)	400	0.22nm

Table 5. By mixing the Mint and Tulsi a combined stock was prepared and the absorbance values of Mixed Stock

Tulsi	Mint	Ascorbic Acid	Mixed Stock
0.19nm	0.16nm	0.16nm	0.18nm

Table 6. H2O2 was used as a reference sample in the whole process. The values of H2O2

Discussion

Determination of radical scavenging activity by H2O2 is a rapid and reliable method to evaluate the antioxidant activity. With this method, it is possible to determine the radical scavenging potential of antioxidants by measuring the absorbance at 400nm. Among all the herbs examined, Tulsi exhibited radical scavenging activity with 0.13 nm, 0.18 nm, 0.08, 0.19 nm; Mint 0.16 nm, 0.22 nm, 0.23 nm, 0.26nm ; Ascorbic Acid 0.07, 0.02nm, 0.04nm, 0.10 and H2O2 0.17nm, 0.16nm, 0.22 nm, 0.18 nm. The result shows that the antioxidant properties of Mint is higher than Tulsi. As shown in methods and methodology sample were combine synergistically to observe their antioxidant properties along with reference. Tusli and Mint both have great importance in our daily life. These both are used for different purposes like medicinal, cookery and industrial. Mostly in medicinal use, for the treatment of different diseases like cancer, ulcer, diabetes, sore throat, headache and many more. A great number of aromatic, medicinal, spice and other plants contain chemical compounds exhibiting antioxidant properties. Oxidative process is one of the most important routes for producing free radicals in foods, drugs and even in living systems. The most effective path to eliminate the effect of oxidative stress is antioxidant properties of Tulsi and Mint. Antioxidant are the substances have potential to break the free radical chain. The antioxidant activity of the plant extracts was examined on the basis of the scavenging effect on the stable H2O2 free radical activity.

Conclusion

Mint and Tusli have great anti-oxidant activity because of their nature. Antioxidant can scavenge the active forms of oxygen involved in the imitation step of oxidation. Antioxidant act as free radicals scavenges, reducing agent chelating agent for transition method. Tusli is used from ancient times to treat several diseases like abdominal issues, oral infections, cough, colds, tumors and cancer, digestive tract problems, respiratory inflammation, arthritis, asthma, ulcers, wounds, hypoglycaemia, bronchitis, urinary issues, cardiovascular problems and many others. Anti-oxidant property of Tulsi is believed to be due to the complexity of constitutes in the plant, leading to many positive influences in the human body. Mint is most widespread herb across the world that is used in medicine, cooking, and household, as well as pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry. Mint is applied as a medication in the form of infusions and teas for treatment of gastroenteric diseases, as demulcent at palpitation, depression and insomnia, in sedatives, as anesthesia at burns and insect stings, as well as analgesic and anti stress medicine.

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